

IET10522, a high-yielding, medium-duration rice for waterlogged conditions

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In Kalkulam and Vilavancode taluks of Kanyakumari district, nearly 10,000 ha of ricefields are waterlogged in both the wet and dry seasons. Standing water depth ranges from 15 to 30 cm throughout the cropping period.

We evaluated four deepwater rice cultures and medium-deep varieties ADT40, CO 42, and H4 for 3 yr, 1987-88 to 1989-90. The trial was laid out in 4 ×

Performance of waterlogging-tolerant cultures at Agricultural Research Station, Thirupathisaram, Tamil Nadu, India, 1987-88 to 1989-90.

Variety	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)				Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle weight (g)	Straw yield (t/ha)
		1987-88	1988-89	1989-90	Mean					
IET10522	RP31-49-2/LMN	4.9	4.1	4.2	4.4	140	102	8	2.19	12.2
IET10205	Manasarovar/CO 14	2.9	3.2	2.4	2.8	130	132	7	1.08	12.3
IET10207	Manasarovar/CO 14	2.2	2.4	1.8	2.1	138	90	7	0.99	10.0
IET10208	RP31-49-2/LMN	2.9	2.6	2.0	2.5	138	94	7	1.20	10.5
H4	—	3.4	2.2	2.3	2.7	137	92	7	1.10	8.4
ADT40	Sona/RP6/13	3.6	3.4	3.1	3.4	138	97	8	1.38	10.0
CO 42	RP31-49-2/LMN	3.5	3.5	2.9	3.3	139	119	8	1.17	9.3
LSD (0.05)		0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5					1.1

3-m plots, with 20 × 10-cm spacing, in a randomized block design with three replications. The nursery was raised in Sep and transplanting was in Oct.

IET10522 (RP31-49-2/LMN) was found promising in all 3 yr (see table).

Mean grain yield was 4.4 t/ha. Yields were 29.5 and 33.8% higher than yields of ADT40 and CO 42, respectively.

IET10522 is medium tall, nonlodging, with long slender white grains. ■

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology

Influence of mycorrhizal association and inorganic nutrients on early growth of rice

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We examined the vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizae (VAM) fungal association of young rice plants and its response to inorganic nutrients.

Seeds of rice variety Lebonnet were obtained from the Louisiana State University Rice Research Station (LSURRS). VAM fungal inoculum (rice roots and rhizosphere soil) was obtained by growing rice plants in soil from LSURRS.

Plants were grown to the early growth stage (50 d) in sterilized soil with mycorrhizal (VAM) and without mycorrhizal (NON-VAM) propagules and supplied with 2.5 ml of nutrient solution at 160 µg/g (nutrient availability after application = 11.2 µg/g) applied every 7 d. Nutrient treatments were P, N, P + N, and deionized water (control).

Table 1. Root and shoot dry weight of rice grown in sterilized soil with inorganic nutrients and VAM fungi.^a

Nutrient treatment	Root dry weight (g)		Shoot dry weight (g)	
	Without VAM	With VAM	Without VAM	With VAM
Phosphorus	1.21 ± 0.31 b	0.44 ± 0.10 a	1.48 ± 0.44 b	0.53 ± 0.12 a
Nitrogen	0.74 ± 0.12 a	0.59 ± 0.09 a	0.80 ± 0.15 a	0.58 ± 0.13 a
Phosphorus + nitrogen	1.25 ± 0.27 b	0.29 ± 0.15 a	1.28 ± 0.25 b	0.37 ± 0.26 a
Deionized water	1.44 ± 0.37 b	0.39 ± 0.23 a	1.42 ± 0.27 b	0.59 ± 0.23 a

^a Mean (X ± SD). In a column, means with the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's mean separation test (p < 0.05).

Plants were watered daily for moisture conditions similar to those of rice seedlings growing in nonflooded fields.

Plants grown in NON-VAM sterilized soil and supplied with P, P + N, and deionized water had significantly higher root and shoot dry weights than plants grown in soil with VAM fungi and the same nutrients (Table 1). There were no differences between the plants supplied with N alone, with or without VAM.

Control plants supplied with deionized water had significantly higher fungi colonization than all other treatments (Table 2).

Plants inoculated with VAM fungi and supplied with P, P + N, and deionized water had significantly lower root and shoot biomass than plants grown in soil without VAM but with the same nutrients. In the NON-VAM treatments, plants

Table 2. VAM colonization of rice roots grown in sterilized soil with inorganic nutrients and VAM fungi inoculum.^a

Nutrient treatment	VAM colonization (%)
Phosphorus	29.76 ± 9.87 a
Nitrogen	32.00 ± 6.53 a
Phosphorus + nitrogen	27.83 ± 7.10 a
Deionized water	43.65 ± 11.33

^a Mean (X ± SD). Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's mean separation test (p < 0.05).

supplied with P and P + N did not differ in biomass from those grown with only deionized water. This may be due to the availability of nutrients upon soil sterilization.

The results of the VAM treatments suggest that colonization by VAM fungi may be a carbon drain on the plant. However, this may be true only during